

LEPTOSPIROSIS IN INDIA: A RE-EMERGING THREAT AND THE NEED FOR A ONE HEALTH STRATEGY

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ABSTRACT

Leptospirosis is a globally prevalent zoonotic disease caused by *Leptospira* spp., with over 300 known pathogenic serovars. It poses serious public health and economic challenges, particularly in tropical and subtropical regions where climatic conditions support its transmission. Humans contract the disease through direct or indirect exposure to urine-contaminated water, soil, or animal tissues, with rodents serving as primary reservoirs and domestic animals acting as secondary hosts. Leptospirosis significantly affects occupational groups such as farmers, veterinarians, and abattoir workers, and contributes to reproductive failures and productivity losses in livestock. Symptoms in both humans and animals range from mild flu-like signs to severe manifestations, including renal and hepatic failure, pulmonary complications, and in some cases, death. Diagnosis relies on both direct detection methods like PCR and culture, and indirect serological techniques, with the microscopic agglutination test (MAT) being the gold standard. Prevention strategies include animal vaccination, antibiotic prophylaxis, rodent control, sanitation, and occupational safety measures. Effective control of the disease requires a One Health strategy because of its intersection at the human-animal-environment interface. In order to enhance surveillance, lower transmission, and put sustainable control measures into place, this interdisciplinary framework encourages coordinated efforts between the medical, veterinary, and environmental sectors. Comprehensive One Health interventions are crucial to mitigating the global impact of leptospirosis.

KEYWORDS: Leptospirosis, one health, transmission, prevention and control

INTRODUCTION

The global zoonotic disease leptospirosis is brought on by *Leptospira* spp. contracted by coming into contact with contaminated water, dirt, or animal urine. With over 300 pathogenic serovars discovered, it poses a threat to both humans and animals. The disease's complexity at the human-animal-environment interface needs a One Health approach, which combines efforts from several sectors to improve epidemiology, transmission, surveillance, prevention, and control techniques. This interdisciplinary collaboration is critical for resolving the numerous issues of leptospirosis and

reducing its public health effect (Sykes *et al.*, 2022).

ETIOLOGY AND EPIDEMIOLOGY

Leptospirosis is a zoonotic illness caused by virulent Gram-negative bacteria under the genus *Leptospira* (Bharti *et al.*, 2003). The two species of the family Leptospiraceae, class Spirochaetes, are *L. interrogans*, comprising all virulent strains of bacteria, and *L. biflexa*, which encompasses saprophytic isolates that are derived from the surroundings. According to Yadeta *et al.* (2016), *L. interrogans* contains a number of common serovars, such as *L. pomona*, *L. canicola*, *L. bratislava*, *L. grippityphosa*, *L. hardjo*, and *L. icterohemorrhagiae*. *L.*